

Multidimensional magnetism model using CPT attributes

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Abstract

This paper would introduce new method to approach magnetism in multidimensional structure of atoms.

1 Introduction

Current understanding of magnetism model is pretty much due to the Ising model. But its limitation in encountering more than single dimensional state makes application of the model to reality restricted.

This paper would describe a model to explain the multidimensional magnetism structure, which would include topological approach by utilizing each fraction of magnetic field assuming bundle of magnetic spin as quasi-particle.

2 Quasiparticle as topological form

Current explanation of quasi-particle is broadly utilized in topological standards. And this usage is accepted as premise in developing quantum computing by explaining field in topological approach.

In this case, reversal approach by explaining magnetism by quasiparticle could be conducted. Assuming that topological manifold m in $\mathbb{C}^n$ could fit in as optimal shape in representing magnetic field F :

$$\begin{aligned} M = \{x \mid x \in \forall \exists m\} &\implies n(M) \neq \infty \\ &\implies n(\text{Basis } \mathbf{B} \text{ for } M) \neq \infty \end{aligned}$$

Therefore, what really needed to be done to model magnetism in a group of spin is to formulate basis vector of magnetism that constitutes the manifold repeating through CPT symmetry and asymmetry.

3 CPT attributes in manifold

So, now that it is clear that formulating basis vector from existing bundle of spin in their form is a key to modeling magnetism, then how could single one of basis vector could be derived from the whole?

The intrinsic limitation in Ising model to premise that assuming the spin directs in single direction at all moments without further interaction with other particles. For overcoming this, spin direction could change throughout time and share its interaction with the other particles:

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Let particle } p, \text{ charge of particle } e_p \text{ at time } t \\ &\implies (\text{As for spin vector}) \left(\text{Larger Field Vector } \overrightarrow{LFV} \right) = \sum \left(\text{Small Field Vector } \overrightarrow{SFV} \right) \end{aligned}$$

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By substitute vector to observation in atom model proposed before[2]:

$$Total\ Spin\ Vector\ \overrightarrow{TSV} = \left(\sum_t^{\forall t} \left(Spin\ vector\ \overrightarrow{SV} \right) \cdot (1 - PE) \cdot (1 - OE) \cdot (1 - ME) \right) + SR - CR$$

And the rest follows as similar[1][2]. As discussed in preceded paper[1], method to formulate interactions in observation by PE, OE, ME could be described in unified form like:

$$\alpha = 1 - PE, \beta = 1 - ME, \gamma = 1 - OE$$

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\beta} \left(\frac{1}{\alpha(\alpha + \beta)} - 1 \right) - 1$$

As the model in this paper is limited in magnetic field, rest of the interactions could be explained as following form:

3.1 Charge symmetry and asymmetry

$$Let\ \sum_t^{\forall t} \overrightarrow{CR} = \left(\sum_t^{\forall t} \left(Spin\ vector\ \overrightarrow{SV} \right) \cdot (PE + a) \cdot (OE + b) \cdot (ME + c) \right)$$

$$\implies \sum_t^{\forall t} \overrightarrow{SR} = \left(\sum_t^{\forall t} \left(Spin\ vector\ \overrightarrow{SV} \right) \cdot (1 - PE - a) \cdot (1 - OE - b) \cdot (1 - ME - c) \right)$$

By ensuring charge symmetry, it gives certain amount of change in error to be corrected by gauge attribute in total observation.

3.2 Parity symmetry and asymmetry

$$\sum_t^{\forall t} \|\overrightarrow{SR}\| - \sum_t^{\forall t} \|\overrightarrow{CR}\| = 0$$

Assuming that all the $1 - PE$, $1 - ME$, $1 - OE$ has its vector attribute as by their native spin[1]:

$$\vec{\alpha} = \overrightarrow{1 - PE}, \vec{\beta} = \overrightarrow{1 - ME}, \vec{\gamma} = \overrightarrow{1 - OE}$$

$$\implies \overrightarrow{TSV} = \sum_t^{\forall t} (\vec{I} - \vec{\gamma}) \cdot \overrightarrow{SV}$$

$$\implies \vec{\alpha} + \vec{\beta} = \vec{I} - \vec{\gamma}$$

$$\implies (\vec{\alpha} + \vec{\beta}) \cdot (\vec{I} + \vec{\beta} + \vec{\beta}\vec{\gamma}) = \vec{I}$$

By charge and parity symmetry, alignment flow in spin arrangement could be formulated. This implies not only decisive spin($\vec{I}$ or $-\vec{I}$) exists, but in form of sum of partial vectors in explaining spin could be conducted.

3.3 Time symmetry and asymmetry

By the nature of charge symmetry and its asymmetry[2]:

$$\sum_t^{\forall t} SR = \sum_t^{\forall t} CR$$

By this attribute in magnetic field, repulsion and attraction between the magnetic fields could be derived. Moreover, this attribute owes its form similar to strong and weak force, binding forces between particles could be related. So to say, at a level of particle size less than an atom, it would be about constituents of particle, but if it takes size more than an atom it would be about combining force between atomic particles.

Than how electric field affects the spin vector? As well known, Maxwell equations could take form.

$$\begin{aligned}\nabla \times \mathbf{E} &= -\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} \\ \nabla \times \mathbf{B} &= \mu_0 \mathbf{J} + \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t}\end{aligned}$$

(Note that $\mathbf{J} = dI/dA$, ϵ is permittivity, μ is permeability.)

(As the equation takes a premise in a level of atomic particle, equation is derived from formation in vacuum.)
By expanding this equation to Lorentz force:

$$F_e + F_m = q(E + \vec{v} \times B)$$

Where q is a charge of particle, v is a velocity of particle. Summing all up, single particle moving in electromagnetic field could be described as:

$$q(\nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \vec{v} \cdot \nabla \times \mathbf{B}) = \nabla \cdot \vec{F}_e + \nabla \cdot \vec{F}_m = q \cdot \left(-\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} + \vec{v} \cdot \mu_0 \frac{\partial I}{\partial A} + \vec{v} \cdot \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \frac{\partial \mathbf{E}}{\partial t} \right)$$

This follows form of Cauchy momentum equation in conservation form as like:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \mathbf{u}) + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \otimes \mathbf{u}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\tau} + \rho \mathbf{g}$$

where p is pressure, $\mathbf{u}$ is velocity of fluid, $\mathbf{g}$ is acceleration from gravity, ρ is permittivity, $\boldsymbol{\tau}$ is a deviatoric stress tensor. Thus, by showing the upper equation derived from Lorentz force is equivalent with Cauchy momentum equation, flows made from of electromagnetic field could be proved to have flow made from Newtonian fluid mechanism, and vice versa.

And so by extending vector to topological manifolds, contour that consists magnetic field could be devised. And the magnetism that consists through electric or further forces could be applied to the manifold.

4 Conclusion

Further approaches could be made to explain magnetic field to unify four default force that consist universe, and these would be discussed in later paper:

- Relation with weak and strong force - upper discussion has limitation that it is based on the magnetic flow within the atom-sized system. What would happen to magnetic field within less than atom-sized system?
- Relation with gravity force - electromagnetic field has its relation implication with gravity field as in preceded discussion[2]. What would happen to gravity with exceptionally large electromagnetic force? Assuming conservation of the field distorted in the electromagnetic field, gravity would be affected, also.
- Unstable fluctuation of magnetism in spin structure - The model discussed in this paper permits possibility of unfixed spin state in a magnetic structure throughout time. And expanding this idea could result in periodically (or spontaneously) self-varying spin vector in time by the non-determined state.

Especially for instability in spin structure itself, this could lead into another understanding of self-magnetization in a sense that unstable state itself devours stable state in general nature.

References

- [1] Jihyeon Yoon. Descriptive Method in Observation and Its Application. 3 2023.
- [2] Jihyeon Yoon. General Specification for Simulating Universe. 3 2023.